

Study of Distribution of Lipid Profile Parameters and hs-CRP in Indian Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease Patients, in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Located in West India

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Received: 25-10-2024 / Revised: 23-11-2024 / Accepted: 26-12-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is an important etiology for development of chronic liver disease worldwide. NAFLD encompasses a range of conditions, including steatosis, steatohepatitis, cirrhosis, and the development of hepatocellular carcinoma. NAFLD is associated with multiple risk factors such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, dyslipidemia, a diet rich in fat, sedentary habits, and a combination of genetic, epigenetic, and environmental influences, with dyslipidemia playing a significant role. Given the observed variations in lipid profile parameters among the Indian population compared to Western populations, our research aims to investigate the distribution of various lipid profile parameters in Indian individuals with NAFLD. Additionally, we plan to assess hs-CRP levels alongside lipid profiles.

Results: Mean age of the study population was 45.3 years ranging from 22 years to 68 years. Dyslipidemia was found in 48 patients in our study population. Mean value of total cholesterol, triglyceride, low-density lipoprotein and high-density lipoprotein were 185.5 mg/dl, 179.2 mg/dl, 120.5 mg/dl and 48.3 mg/dl respectively. Total cholesterol, triglyceride and low-density lipoprotein were increased in 38.3%, 56.7% and 38.3% respectively. High-density lipoprotein was decreased in 23.3% cases. The study showed elevated hs-CRP levels in 53 patients. The median value of hs-CRP was 6.36 mg/L and the interquartile range was 11.55 mg/L. Among 60 patients enrolled in the study, 27 were detected with NAFLD as an incidental finding. The rest of the patients had different symptoms related to NAFLD. No association was found between dyslipidemia and elevation of hs-CRP levels in our sample of NAFLD patients.

Conclusion: Dyslipidemia in the form of hypertriglyceridemia is common among Indian NAFLD patients. Although dyslipidemia occurs along with hs-CRP elevation in NAFLD patients, the degree of hs-CRP elevation doesn't correlate with degree or type of dyslipidemia, indicating the presence of other factors besides dyslipidemia in the development of inflammation in NAFLD.

Keywords: dyslipidemia, liver diseases, NAFLD, fatty liver, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.

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Introduction

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) is defined by the presence of steatosis in over 5% of hepatocytes, associated with metabolic risk factors (particularly, obesity and type 2 diabetes) and absence of significant alcohol consumption (>30 g per day for men and >20 g per day for women) or other chronic liver diseases [1]. NAFLD is currently the most common liver disease worldwide, affecting about 25% of general population. The highest prevalence rates are observed in the Middle East (32%) and South America (31%) and lowest rates in Africa (14%) [2]. The prevalence in Asia is 27 % [2] and in India the prevalence is observed to be 9-53% [3], in

different studies. Easy access to calorie dense food and sedentary lifestyle, together with the modern epidemics of diabetes mellitus and obesity have catapulted Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease into a substantial public health problem in India as in other parts of the world. NAFLD has emerged as one of the leading causes of cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and liver transplant in India [3]. Thus, its recent integration into National Program on Prevention and Control of Cancer, Diabetes, Cardiovascular and Stroke by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of India [4]. NAFLD is associated with obesity, type 2 diabetes, dyslipidemia, fat -rich diet, sedentary lifestyle,

genetic, epigenetic, environmental factors [5]. It has also been shown that Asian Indians have a higher body fat percentage and an adverse body fat pattern including abdominal adiposity even when the BMI is within currently defined normal limits. Previous studies on Indian NAFLD patients have observed that even though overweight or obese and central obesity are quite common in Indians in comparison to the west, extreme forms of obesity, diabetes mellitus and hypertension are less common [6]. Dyslipidemia is an important risk factor for NAFLD and is estimated to be present in 69% NAFLD patients [2], in western studies. The dyslipidemia pattern observed in Indian patients is reported to be different from the west. Studies on Indian Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) patients have demonstrated that in comparison to Caucasian population, Indian CAD patients have a relatively lower level of cholesterol [7]. Triglyceride levels are generally observed to be high in Indians, in comparison to the western population [8]. Increased prevalence of low HDL has been reported by Enas et al who found that only 4% and 5 % Asian Indian men and women respectively had optimal HDL levels [9].

In view of the above observed differences in lipid profile distribution in Indians, in the general population as well as in different disease states, when compared to western standards, we intend to study the distribution of different lipid profile parameters in Indian NAFLD patients. High sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) is produced by liver cells and is part of the body's acute-phase response. It tends to increase non-specifically in the presence of bacterial infections, immune-inflammatory conditions, and malignancies. Obesity, particularly excess abdominal fat, is associated with a mild, chronic inflammatory state throughout the body. Studies suggest that elevated hs-CRP levels may have predictive value for the development of metabolic syndrome [10], type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) [11], and coronary heart disease (CHD) [12]. Additionally, increased hs-CRP levels have been associated with both overall and abdominal fat accumulation in various studies involving Asian Indians [13].

Current knowledge about the development of NAFLD and NASH follows a two-step concept. Initially, impaired liver response to insulin leads to the accumulation of fat (steatosis). Subsequently, external triggers induce oxidative stress and the production of cytokines, resulting in liver inflammation. Importantly, systemic subclinical inflammation can arise from both liver inflammation and visceral fat. Recent research suggests that hs-CRP may serve as a biomarker for NAFLD in specific populations, such as the Japanese [14], although this connection hasn't been firmly established in other groups, such as

Europeans [15]. In view of the paucity of information about lipid profile and hs-CRP in Indian NAFLD patients, we plan to estimate hs-CRP levels in conjunction with lipid profile, in our cohort of NAFLD patients, to evaluate the distribution of these parameters in Indian NAFLD patients.

Methods

A total of 60 patients were included in the study between March 2023 and May 2023. The study cohort included 51 females and 9 males. The study participants were recruited from patients who underwent ultrasonography of the abdomen at the radiology department of G.M.E.R.S Medical College and Hospital, a teaching tertiary care institution in Vadodra, Gujarat, India. Patients having fatty liver on ultrasound examination were the potential study cohort. They were further questioned, and their medical history was studied intensively to identify the existence of any exclusion criteria. The exclusion criteria used were existence of acute or chronic liver diseases including viral hepatitis A, C, B, alcohol consumption (men more than 30 g /day and women more than 20 g/day), coronary artery disease, pregnancy, lactation, taking medications that affect the liver like steroid, amiodarone, anti - tubercular drugs, anti -retro-viral drugs, tamoxifen. The patients selected to be part of the study were explained the nature of the study, its significance and were included in the study only after taking the patient's informed consent. Approval from the institutional ethics committee was taken before starting the research. Ultrasound examinations were performed on Philips affinity 50 G using high resolution B mode. The diagnosis of NAFLD was made by the examining radiologist who followed the standardized procedure. The diagnosis was made based on increased liver parenchymal echogenicity with impaired visualization of normally echogenic walls of intrahepatic portal venous branches. Increased echogenicity of the liver was detected by comparison to the adjacent kidney. Patient details were collected using a case record form containing four sections, one each for patient demographics, alcohol consumption, medical history and medication history. The study participants were asked to present at the Common collection center of the hospital in fasting state for collection of blood samples for lipid profile estimation (serum total cholesterol, serum triglyceride, serum HDL, serum LDL) and hs- CRP level estimation. All biochemical testing was performed on the Erba EM360 Fully automated Chemistry Analyzer, using Transasia-Erba reagent kits. The hs-CRP parameter was estimated using a reagent kit manufactured by AGD diagnostics, based on the principle of Immunoturbidimetry. Interpretation of laboratory tests was done using

following criteria:1) Dyslipidemia was defined as the presence of any one or more lipid profile parameters above the reference range. The reference ranges used for this interpretation were Total cholesterol >200 mg/dl, Triglyceride >150 mg/dl, LDL>130 mg/dl and HDL C (≤ 40 mg / dl / in men and ≤ 50 mg / dl in women's). 2) The hs-CRP cut-off of > 1.0 mg/L was used to identify patients with increased hs-CRP levels. The results were recorded on Microsoft excel sheet. Preliminary statistical analysis such as Mean,

standard deviation, and preparation of charts was done using Microsoft excel. For advanced statistical analysis the statistical calculators on the website Social Sciences Statistics were used. (Website: www.socscistatistics.com.)

Results

A total of 60 ultrasonographically diagnosed NAFLD cases were included in the study. Table 1 summarizes the distribution of demographic data and study variables in the cohort.

Table 1: Summary of distribution of demographic data and study variables in the NAFLD cohort.

Parameters	Mean	Standard deviation
Age	45.3 years	11.6
Gender ratio (M: F)	9: 51	-
Total cholesterol	185.5 mg/dl	39.8
Triglyceride	179.2 mg/dl	92.6
High-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol	48.3 mg/dl	11.9
Low- density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol	120.5 mg/dl	29.1

The mean age of males (n = 9) was 43.8 years and that of females (n = 51) was 45.6 years. The majority of patients were in the 38-47 years age group, n = 22 (36.67%), as depicted in Figure 1

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to age groups.

The mean concentration total cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C were within optimum levels in the study population. The mean concentration of Triglyceride levels in the study population was higher than reference range.

The hs-CRP levels in the study population range from a minimum of 0.01 mg/L to a maximum of 105.69 mg/L. The median value of hs-CRP is 6.36

mg/L, and the interquartile range is 11.55 mg/L. Table 2 summarizes the presentation of the NAFLD patients. For 27 cases out of the 60 cases enrolled in the study NAFLD was an incidental finding.

The remaining 33 cases had symptoms related to NAFLD, which prompted the ultrasound investigation.

Table 2: Prevalence of symptoms in NAFLD patients.

Symptoms	Number of Patients	Percentage
Symptomatic (abdominal pain)	33	55 %
Incidental finding	27	45 %

Table 3 summarizes the percentage of individuals in the study population who had lipid profile parameters above or below the optimum levels. As

observed in Table 1, here again we see that elevated Triglyceride is the most common dyslipidemic parameter. Patients with

hypercholesterolemia were likely to have associated elevation of Triglyceride too. 86.9% of hypercholesterolemia subjects have associated hypertriglyceridemia and 78.2 % subjects have associated LDL elevation. Hypertriglyceridemia subjects have 58.8 % likelihood of having associated hypercholesterolemia and elevation of

LDL-C. Elevation of Total Cholesterol and LDL often happens together.

Decrease HDL was the least frequent dyslipidemic feature in fatty liver patients, but when present was associated with increased triglyceride in 50 % patients.

Table 3: Summary of patients having abnormal lipid profile parameters in the NAFLD cohort.

Serum lipid profile parameters (mg/dl)	No. of cases with values beyond reference range (%)	Cases with associated increased serum Cholesterol	Cases with associated increased serum Triglycerides	Cases with associated increased serum Low density (LDL) lipoprotein cholesterol	Cases with associated decreased serum High density (HDL) lipoprotein cholesterol
Total cholesterol (N<200 mg/dl)	23 (38.3%)	NA	20	18	3
Triglyceride (N<150 mg/dl)	34 (56.7%)	20	NA	19	8
High-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol (N>40 mg/dl in female and >50 mg/dl in males)	14 (23.3%)	1	7	1	NA
Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol (N<130 mg/dl)	23(38.3%)	18	19	NA	1

There are 12 NAFLD patients in our study who have completely normal lipid profiles. Rest of the 48 patients have a combination of dyslipidemic features. As shown in Table 4, no significant association was found between hs-CRP and any of the lipid parameters (total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-C, and HDL-C).

Table 4: Correlation of hs- CRP with Lipid profile parameters using chi-square

Lipid Profile Parameters	Chi – Square statistic	p – value
Total cholesterol	0.911	0.339
Triglyceride	0.003	0.954
LDL-C	0.734	0.391
HDL -C	2.157	0.141

Discussion

The incidence of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is increasing in India due to rising affluence and the shift away from traditional lifestyles. This hospital-based observational, cross-sectional study included USG-diagnosed cases of NAFLD. In the current study, an attempt was made to describe the distribution of lipid levels among patients with NAFLD in a Tertiary care hospital, situated in western part of India. In our study the age of the patients ranged from 22 years to 68 years with mean age of 45.3 (SD = 11.6). Mean age in males was 43.8 years and mean age in females was 45.6 years. In other Indian studies the mean age of patients was 42.90+10.54 years, and the age

distribution of the population was similar to our study [16]. In western studies the mean age of the study population was 49.7 ± 10.6 years [17]. Most patients were in the age group 28-47 years (as per figure 1). This study thus demonstrated that Indian NAFLD patients tended to be younger and were typically diagnosed at an earlier age compared to their counterparts in the United States.

In our study 27 patients were asymptomatic (45 %) which was a little higher compared to other Indian studies (30.8-38%). Western studies have reported 47.7 to 64% patients to be asymptomatic [18]. 33 (55%) patients presented with the symptom of abdominal pain, which was investigated with an Ultrasound scan of the abdomen, resulting in the

diagnosis of NAFLD. A study by Amrapurkar et al [19] documented that 69.23% of symptomatic patients reported right hypochondrial pain as their primary complaint, a percentage that exceeded the findings in our own study. The mean value of total

cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-C, HDL-C in our study are 185.5 mg/dl, 179.2 mg/dl, 120.5 mg/dl, 48.3 mg respectively. Table 5 compares values observed in our study with those reported from previous research.

Table 5: Compares the lipid profile distribution observed in our study with other similar studies.

Study	Year	Number of subjects	Diagnosis of NAFLD based on	Mean Cholesterol	Mean Triglyceride	Mean Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol	Mean High-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol
Swain et al [20]	2015	939	USG	185.3 ± 52.9	199.0 ± 115.8	109.1 ± 38.3	44.3 ± 16.3
Sen A et al	2013	385	USG	181.89±55.22	203.81±33.55	114.88±41.88	60.4±32.48
Roli Agrawal et al.	2009	124	USG	207.32 ± 5.87	178.64 ± 61.18	115.78 ± 35.49	45.36 ± 11.06
Baghel et al	2023	50	USG	185.10± 46.76	161.15±46.30	105.75±45.96	47.12±6.86
current study	2023	60	USG	185.5 ± 39.8 mg/dl	179.2 ± 92.6 mg/dl	120.5± 29.1 mg/dl	48.3±11.9 mg

In our study, increased serum total cholesterol, increased triglyceride and increased LDL were observed in 23 (38.3%), 34 (56.7%), 23(38.3%) of NAFLD cases respectively. Similarly, decreased serum HDL was seen in 14 (23.3%) of the study population. The percentage of patients with elevated Triglyceride and LDL-C in the study conducted by Sen et al [21] is similar to the percentage observed in our study. Cholesterol levels were also similar to the findings in the study by Duseja et al, which reported hypercholesterolemia in 32% of their patients. Similar cholesterol values were observed in the study conducted by Roli Agrawal et al [16].

In comparison to the reported dyslipidemia in the study by Swain et al, our study subjects were found to have lower Triglyceride levels but higher LDL-C levels, with comparable Total cholesterol levels.

The hs-CRP levels in our study group ranged from 0.01 mg/L to 105.69 mg/L. Median value being 6.36 mg/L. The current study showed elevated hs-CRP levels in 53 patients (88.3%). We observed 7 (11.7 %) of our study subjects had normal hs-CRP (that is < 1 mg/L). In the study by Nigam P et al [22], 23% of the NAFLD patients were found to have hs-CRP < 1 mg/L. In our study, out of the 7 subjects with normal hs-CRP, 5 study subjects had elevation of Triglycerides and 4 of them had associated LDL-C elevation. One subject has isolated elevation of cholesterol level.

The above observations possibly indicate the existence of multiple pathophysiological processes which culminate in the development of NAFLD. It is possible that some patients had normal hs-CRP because of early identification of fatty liver, before

beginning the inflammatory process. There was one study subject who had completely normal lipid profile and hs-CRP level of 0.01mg/L, who was coincidentally observed to have a high HDL level of 75 mg/dl. Such patients will need to be further investigated about the cause of NAFLD development. On the contrary such patients may be found to have better recovery or reversal of fatty liver changes on long term follow-up. The significance of this observation can be understood only by long term follow-up study of such patients.

In summary, NAFLD is a relatively common liver disease, and research studies have been published analyzing the association of various risk factors such as dyslipidemia, obesity, dietary habits etc. with the occurrence of NAFLD. Our study showed the presence of dyslipidemia in NAFLD patients, with hypertriglyceridemia being the most common dyslipidemic feature (56.7%) and elevation of hs-CRP levels in most patients (88.3%).

The data concurrently highlights the occurrence of NAFLD even in the absence of recognizable risk factors, as evidenced by normal lipid profile in 20% of NAFLD patients and normal hs-CRP in 11.6% of NAFLD patients. These observations highlight the need to further study NAFLD using a systems approach, where the interaction of these multiple risk factors in the development of NAFLD can be evaluated.

Our research has certain limitations as NAFLD was diagnosed using ultrasonography, which, while commonly used, is not considered the gold standard; liver biopsy is, but it's invasive, costly, and can carry risks. Also, due to the limited sample size and the single hospital setting of our research,

the study's findings can be considered as preliminary observations to develop larger, more targeted studies, to understand NAFLD pathophysiology. In the future, a more extensive cohort study is recommended, encompassing a broader range of variables, a larger participant pool, and inclusion of individuals from the general community to provide further elucidation on this subject.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings from this research demonstrate elevation of cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL and hs-CRP among individuals with NAFLD. Hypertriglyceridemia is the common dyslipidemia observed. Further the severity of inflammation doesn't correlate with degree or type of dyslipidemia, indicating the role of multiple factors besides dyslipidemia in the development of NAFLD.

These findings underscore the complexity of NAFLD etiology and emphasize the need for further exploration into the various contributing factors involved.

List of abbreviations-

NAFLD- Non- Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease

hs- CRP- high sensitivity C - reactive protein

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate- Consent was obtained or waived by all participants in this study. Institutional Human Ethics Committee, GMERS Medical College & Hospital, Gotri, Vadodara issued approval IHEC/22/OUT/SRUG010.

As the research study classifies in the minimal risk category, the IHEC GMERS approves your study to be conducted in the presented form.

Acknowledgements: We thank the participants, the Biochemistry Department, and the Radiology Department of the GMERS Medical College, Vadodara for their support in this study. We are highly thankful to Dr. Vijay N. Vaidya, HOD, Department of Radiology, GMERS Medical College, Vadodara.; Dr. Vijay Ladumor Samatbhai, Department of Radiology, GMERS Medical College, Vadodara.; Dr. Suresh kumar. M, Department of Radiology, GMERS Medical College, Vadodara.

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